

UZBEK CUSTOMS AND TRADITIONS: A SPIRITUAL HERITAGE LEFT OVER FROM CENTURIES

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Abstract: This article provides detailed information about the Uzbek nation, the national traditions, values, and customs that have been formed and widely used by the Uzbek nation for many years. Information is also provided about the ancient and modern customs of the Uzbek nation, as well as about the traditions that have been preserved for many years and have been changed. It discusses the customs that have been practiced by the Uzbeks since ancient times: marriage ceremonies, hospitality, neighborliness, holidays, and family rituals. Their place and importance in society are shown, and it is emphasized that they should be preserved and passed on to future generations.

Keywords: nationality, values, rituals, Soviet era, address, atlas.

Аннотация: В статье представлена подробная информация об узбекском народе, о национальных традициях, ценностях и обычаях, которые формировались и широко использовались узбекским народом на протяжении многих лет. Также дается информация о древних и современных обычаях узбекского народа, а также о традициях, сохраняющихся на протяжении многих лет и претерпевших изменения. В статье рассматриваются обычаи, которые соблюдались узбеками с древнейших времен: брачные обряды, гостеприимство, добрососедство, праздники и семейные обряды. Показываются их место и значение в обществе, подчеркивается необходимость их сохранения и передачи будущим поколениям.

Ключевые слова: национальность, ценности, ритуалы, советская эпоха, адрес, атлас.

Annotatsiya: Bu maqolada o'zbek millatining, o'zbek millatining ancha yillardan beri shakllanib, keng qo'llanilib kelayotgan milliy an'analari, qadriyatlar va urf-odatlar haqida batafsil ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. O'zbek millatining qadimiy va zamonaviy urf-odatlar, ko'p yillardan beri saqlanib kelayotgan, o'zgartirilgan an'analar haqida ham ma'lumotlar berilgan. Unda o'zbeklarning qadimdan amal qilib kelgan udumlari: nikoh marosimlari, mehmondo'stlik, qo'shnichilik, bayramlar va

oilaviy marosimlar haqida fikrlar yuritiladi. Ularning jamiyatdagi tutgan o'rni, ahamiyati ko'rsatilib, ularni asrab-avaylash va kelajak avlodga yetkazib berish kerakligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: milliylik, qadriyatlar, marosimlar, sovet davri, adras, atlas.

The Uzbek nation! It is a nation that has shed so much blood, endured so much suffering, and received the sun's rays for its honest work and sincere actions before it realized its identity. It is a nation that has not lost its identity or betrayed its identity even in difficult situations. It is a nation that has sweated so much to reach today. It is a nation that has suffered and been oppressed for its efforts towards freedom. But despite all these difficulties, it has strived forward, united to achieve its goals, freedom, and has not even betrayed its national values and traditions.

The Uzbek nation also has traditions that have been ingrained in its soul for many years! The Uzbek nation has spread its fame throughout the world with its traditions such as nationality, values, hospitality, and tolerance. It is not difficult to recognize a person of Uzbek nationality in other countries, because, first of all, his national costume, style of dressing, and then his manners make one doubt his Uzbekness. The Uzbek people have their own traditions, appropriate for each situation. For example, they are associated with family life, the birth and upbringing of children (crib wedding, circumcision wedding), and marriage (fatiha wedding).

These traditions have also been honed for many years. These values are of great importance in preserving and strengthening family ties, in shaping the identity of each person. They reflect respect for inheritance and continuity, maintain stability, and convey important cultural and moral guidelines to future generations. Family traditions create a unique basis for communication and mutual relations between family members. This can be shared holidays, shared dinners, rituals, or family events that help create a warm and friendly atmosphere in the family. Adherence to these traditions helps to: Relationships between relatives are further strengthened by creating emotional bonds and a sense of unity; Family values, such as kindness, respect, tolerance, hard work, and other values formed in the family, encourage family members to unite and come together.

The traditions of the Uzbek nation are reflected not only in the family, but also in every sphere, for example: mosques, tea houses, markets, breakfast soup, national holidays, Navruz holiday, bride's greetings, etc. There are some unique traditions. Such traditions are an integral part of the Uzbek nation. Such traditions also have their own history. Especially during the Soviet era, the Uzbek people faced many difficulties. Many of our national values were restricted.

They created obstacles for our people to understand their identity, to strive for independence and freedom. But despite these difficulties, the Uzbek people managed to preserve their nationality, identity, and many of their traditions. Restricted customs continued in secret and have survived to this day. During the period of independence, the Uzbek people were able to gain freedom, and some national values were restored. Concepts such as patriotism, independence, and spirituality entered our language. Nowadays, our traditions are: Tolerance and hospitality. Uzbekistan is a multinational country.

Representatives of more than 130 nationalities and ethnic groups live in harmony in our country. In addition, they have ensured their peaceful and safe coexistence. This is also a clear manifestation of the tolerance of our nation. Good neighborly traditions. There are also wise sayings and proverbs of the Uzbeks about neighbors. For example, “If you don’t take a house, take a neighbor,” “A distant relative is better than a nearby neighbor,” etc. The Uzbek people are close to their neighbors as if they were relatives. They help each other, stand by each other in difficult situations and in happy times. So, a person’s good relations with his neighbors also bring great benefits. Family and marriage customs are ancient values.

Customs such as matchmaking, marriage, dowry collection, greeting the bride, wedding, wedding, cradle wedding, and sunnat wedding are an integral part of Uzbek national traditions. They are events held among the people, together with the community. These are customs that encourage unity and harmony not only among all family members, but also among the entire society. Various ceremonies and holidays: Navruz holiday, Eid al-Fitr, going to the mosque to pray, and giving alms to widows and the poor.

Navruz holiday is celebrated together with the whole nation. On it, our people prepare sweet dishes from national dishes: sumalak, halim, and koksomsa. They go to visit the elderly, the sick, and ask about their condition. So, this holiday is considered a holiday of the spring equinox and a holiday of renewal and rejuvenation. On Eid, everyone wears new clothes, goes to the mosque and prays. Everyone waits for this holiday with their families. Women cook various dishes and set the table. Children also look forward to this holiday. People distribute charity and exchange gifts with each other. So, this holiday is also celebrated with joy and harmony.

Respect for elders. The Uzbek people, first of all, prefer to treat elders with respect. This is reflected in a person's behavior and manners. Greeting etiquette is the beginning of all human interaction, treatment and communication. What kind of behavior a person has is also evident from his greeting. National clothes, food and

music. The Uzbek nation has a nationality that distinguishes it from other nations. This is reflected in their clothes and food. Uzbek national clothes suit every Uzbek girl. They are sewn from fabrics such as satin and adras, and such clothes are famous all over the world. Special attention is even paid to headwear.

For ceremonial events, there are elegant hats - they are rich in bright and colorful embroidery and patterns, gold embroidery. In addition, such professions as weaving, sewing, embroidery are very developed. Girls also learn these professions as an additional profession. Traditional Uzbek dishes such as samsa, osh and kebab are widespread all over the world. These dishes are prepared for every holiday and make the table attractive and festive. Uzbek melodies and songs are associated with the people's rituals, holidays, various ceremonies, customs, traditions, lifestyle. The most famous songs are: “Kelin salom” (“Kelin salom”), wedding “Yor-yor”, “Ulan”, “Alla” and others.

In conclusion, it should be said that each tradition of the Uzbek nation has been formed over the years and is an important factor regulating and developing the social, spiritual and cultural life of the nation and society. These customs encourage a person to be kind, do good, strengthen such qualities as respect and honor among people. Even if times change, even if circumstances change, even if we change, they are a reminder of our identity, who we are, encouraging us to the right path, a legacy left by our ancestors. We must pass them on to the next generation, and each of us is responsible for this. After all, as long as we have traditions, our nation and its spirit will live forever.

References:

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